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STYLISTIC-SEMANTIC CHARACTERISTICS OF WORDS WITH SOUND CHANGE IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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ABSTRACT

In the article, the connotative meanings related to sound reduction in the pronunciation of words are studied in English and Uzbek languages. Connotation is an additional meaning to the semantics of language units, which expresses the linguopragmatic and methodological attitude of the subject of speech to existence. Such relations have various manifestations, from which additional meanings in phonetic phenomena such as apheresis and elision have been elaborated.

In particular, since the pronunciation of apheresis has connotative meanings such as certain speech lightness, gentleness, tenderness, it is revealed that they are actively used in the speech of characters in the artistic image.

The connotative meanings of the phenomenon of elision in the two languages are analyzed on the basis of factual examples taken from the fiction literature of both languages.

They show that connotative meanings such as brevity, excitement, melodiousness of rhythm, correctness of rhyme, gentleness, passion are expressed in speech.

Key words: pragmatics, pronunciation, elision, syllable, phonetic phenomena, phonostylistics, apheresis, phonostyleme, connotation.

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ИНГЛИЗ ВА ЎЗБЕК ТИЛЛАРИДА ТОВУШ ЎЗГАРИШЛИ СЎЗЛАРНИНГ СТИЛИСТИК-СЕМАНТИК ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Мақолада сўзлар талаффузида товуш туширилиши билан боғлиқ коннотатив маънолар инглиз ва ўзбек тилларида чоғиштириб ўрганилган. Коннотация тил бирликлари семантикасига доир қўшимча маъновий мавжудлик бўлиб, у нутқ субъектининг борлиққа лингвопрагматик ва услубий муносабатини ифода этади. Бундай муносабатлар турли хил

кўринишларга эга бўлиб, улардан аферезис ва элизия каби фонетик ходисаларидаги кўшимча маънолар ҳақида атрофлича фикр юритилган.

Жумладан, аферезислар талаффузида маълум нутқий енгиллик, мулойимлик, нозиклик каби коннотатив маънолар бўлганлиги учун улар бадий тасвирда персонажлар нутқида фаол қўлланилиши очиб берилган.

Элизия ходисасининг чоғиштирилаётган тиллардаги коннотатив маънолари ҳар икки тилдаги бадий адабиётлардан олинган фактик мисоллар асосида таҳлил қилинган.

Уларда нутқда қисқалик, ҳаяжон, ритм оҳангдорлиги, қофияни ростлаш, мулойимлик, эхтирос каби коннотатив маънолар ифодаланганлиги кўрсатилган.

Калит сўзлар: прагматика, талаффуз, элизия, бўғин, фонетик ходисалар, фоностилистика, аферезис, фоностилема, коннотация.

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СТИЛИСТИКО-СЕМАНТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ СЛОВ СО ЗВУКОИЗМЕНЕНИЯМИ В АНГЛИЙСКОМ И УЗБЕКСКОМ ЯЗЫКАХ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье исследуются коннотативные значения, связанные с опусканием звука в произношении слов в английском и узбекском языках. Коннотация-это дополнительное духовное присутствие в семантике языковых единиц, выражающее лингвопрагматическое и методологическое отношение субъекта речи к бытию. Такие отношения имели различные формы, из которых наиболее подробно рассматривались дополнительные значения в их фонетических явлениях, такие как аферезис и элизия.

В частности, поскольку аферезы в произношении имеют определенные коннотативные значения, такие как речевая легкость, мягкость, нежность, то выявлено, что они активно используются в речи персонажей в художественном изображении.

Коннотативные значения явления Элизии в сопоставимых языках были проанализированы на основе фактических примеров из художественной литературы на обоих языках.

Они показывают, что в речи выражены такие коннотативные значения, как краткость, волнение, мелодичность ритма, корректировка рифмы, нежность, страсть.

Ключевые слова: прагматика, произношение, элизия, слог, фонетические явления, фоностилистика, аферезис, фоностилема, коннотация.

Introduction. There are many phonetic processes (changes) in pronunciation. Such words are called by different names in linguistics: phonetic phenomena, phonetic processes, phonetic changes, phonostylistic phenomena, phonostylemes, etc [1, 49].

In general linguistics, including European and Uzbek linguistics, phonetic phenomena in the language have been thoroughly and comprehensively interpreted. Nevertheless, in the scientific research conducted in this field, there is little information about the connotative meanings and their stylistic features that arise due to the pronunciation of words with phonetic changes in the languages being compared. However, it is important to determine the connotative meanings that appear in the pronunciation of words and grammatical forms of English and Uzbek languages and use them in the speech process.

Not enough information is given about the additional, i.e., connotative meanings associated with the pronunciation of sounds in the English and Uzbek languages, which we have taken as the

object of our research. However, deeper study and scientific research of connotative meanings in the pronunciation of phonetic phenomena has important theoretical and practical value.

In words with phonetic changes, two cases are noticeable in terms of form and content: a) pronunciation by adding a sound or syllable: prosthesis, epenthesis, epithesis; b) pronouncing by dropping a sound or syllable: apheresis, syncope, apocope. Each of them has a separate connotative meaning.

In the next period, a number of scientific works related to the research of the emotional-expressive features of the language appeared in Uzbek linguistics. In particular, the research of the connotative meanings of lexical and grammatical units was thoroughly investigated [2, 22]. Connotative meanings in phonetic phenomena are thoroughly researched in A. Haydarov's candidate thesis [3, 122].

The basis for conducting semiotic, semasiological and stylistic research is prepared by studying language units representing denotative and connotative meanings in the language. Further study of scientific research in this direction, a comparative analysis of the connotative meaning from the point of view of unrelated English and Uzbek languages is one of the important tasks facing linguists today [4, 40].

Connotation is an additional meaningful existence included in the semantics of language units, which expresses the semantic-stylistic and functional-stylistic relationship of the subject of speech to existence. Such relations are characteristic of all words with phonetic changes.

This article discusses the phenomena of apheresis and elision, which represent additional meanings associated with the phenomenon of sound dropping in the pronunciation of words.

Main part. The term aphaeresis entered the English language in the middle of the 16th century. This term is also found in some sources in the form of aphasis. Aphasis is often used to refer to the dropping of the first vowel in a word, while apheresis is the dropping of any first syllable at the beginning of a word [5, 60].

Apheresis is a term in the art of oratory and phonology that refers to the dropping of one or more sounds or syllables from the beginning of a word. Its adjective form is also called aphetic or rarely aphaeretic. Apheresis takes two forms.

Sound reduction in pronunciation: *possum – (o)possum, squire – (e)squire, adder – (n)adder, cute – (a)cute, lone – (a)lone, sample – (e)xample, state – (e)state, round – (a)round, ‘mid – (a)mid, pon – (u)pon.*

Syllable reduction in pronunciation: *copter – (heli)copter, plane – (air)plane, coon – (rac)coon, till – (un)til, vantage – (ad)vantage etc.*

In the process of learning to speak, the child is used to retaining only the last one or two syllables of words. As a result, he pronounces the following words like *nette – (mario)nette, range – (o)range, anna – (n)anna, octor – (d)octor*. Such a pronunciation gives the connotation of gentle expression in the child's speech. Apheresis in the child's speech causes irregular pronunciation due to speech thrift, haste, and shortages as well. At the same time, this creates the connotation of melodiousness characteristic of children's speech: *'xactly – (e)xactly, 'tention! – (at)tention!*

Apheresis, similar to apocope, is used as an artistic tool.

“It includes words and expressions spoken in a colloquial style, often deviating from the literary norm”, – writes B.M. Dupriez [6, 235].

Apheresis (aphetic) words mainly form connotative meanings specific to the style of colloquial speech: *drawing-room – (with)drawing-room, fend – (de)fend, stain – (di)stain, sport – (di)sport, peal – (ap)peal, mend – (a)mend, fray – (af)fray, ply – (ap)ply, live – (a)live, spy – (e)spy.*

Dropping of syllables is common in spoken English. In the case of apheresis, connotative meanings such as haste, confusion, shame, hesitation and awkwardness are realized in the interaction between people. Such a situation often occurs as a result of the loss of vowels under the influence of unstressed syllables at the beginning of words. Apheresis is common in contemporary English colloquial speech and fiction: *How 'bout that?... I ain't going 'less you do... [7, 45].*

In the example, by saying the word *about* in the form of *'bout*, the meanings of pleasure, concern, compliment, and kindness are expressed, while the pronunciation of the word *unless* in the form of *'less* shows connotative meanings such as freedom, care, calmness, and restraint.

Since the pronunciation of apheresis has additional meanings, such as certain speech lightness, gentleness, tenderness, they are actively used in the speech of characters in the artistic image. This can be clearly seen in the following text:

“I can't kill the *possum* [(o)*possum*], *'cause* [(be)*cause*] it might be innocent. I can't let the *possum* go, because it might be guilty. Can't make a good soup, can't do a handstand in a pool. Can't spell the word 'lieutenant'. There are a lot of *cant's* in my life right now”.

The phenomenon of apheresis in words is antonymous to phonetic phenomena such as prosthesis, syncope, apocope, due to its specific phonetic form and content.

From the points stated above, it can be seen that if the phenomenon of apheresis is used more in English, in Uzbek this phenomenon occurs in the form of dropping a consonant sound at the beginning of some words: *iraq* - (y)*iraq*, *il* - (y)*il*, *igit* - (y)*igit*, *iring* - (y)*iring*, *igirma* - (y)*igirma* etc.

In the pronunciation of such words, the connotative meaning characteristic of the colloquial speech is understood. And in the artistic image, it is used as a means of characterizing the speech of the characters.

Thus, the cross analysis of apheresis showed that if one sound or more than one syllable is dropped at the beginning of the words pronounced in English, only the speech sound in some words is dropped in Uzbek.

From the above considerations, it can be seen that apheresis is an important phonopragmatic phenomenon in phonostylistics and is characterized by the expression of various connotative meanings. Determining and using such phonopragmatic meanings is of great importance in the process of oral speech and in translation studies [8, 442].

Elision. Based on the general content of various linguistic dictionaries and scientific views, it is appropriate to use the term elision in the meanings of squeezing, pushing out, cutting off. In other words, pronunciation refers to sounds and syllables that have been decreased, eliminated and left out in the word structure.

In spoken English, elision also occurs as a result of dropping one of the following voiceless consonants and reducing or shortening vowels when speaking in haste.

Such words with elision express the connotative meanings of haste, hurry and rush characteristic of the speaker, as shown in the example of the following words in D.Jones's “English Pronouncing Dictionary”: *acts* /æks/, *perhaps* /pə'hæps, præps/, *potato* /pə'teɪtəʊ/, *bicycle* /'baɪsɪkl/, *philosophy* /fɪ'lɒsəfi/ [9, 399].

Elision as a phonostylistic tool is also used to characterize children's speech. For example, the phrase “*left leg*” is pronounced as /lɛflɛg/ and the sound «t» is dropped, while the combination of the word *robbed* and the article «the» is pronounced /rɒbdðə/ and the sound «d» is dropped. In the pronunciation of the combination of the preposition «in» and the word *box*, the sound «n» is dropped and it is pronounced /ɪbɒks/. Such pronunciation in children's speech is explained by the difficulty in pronouncing the above-mentioned words.

Words with elision are used in the speech of characters in fiction. For example, words with elision are used with great skill in the play “*Doctor Faustus*” by Christopher Marlowe:

Settle thy studies, Faustus, and begin
To sound the depth of that thou wilt profess:
Having **commenc'd**, be a divine in show,
Sweet Analytics, 'tis thou hast **ravish'd** me!
Is, to dispute well, logic's chiefest end?
Then read no more; thou hast **attain'd** that end:
Be a physician, Faustus; heap up gold,
Why, Faustus, hast thou not attain'd that end?
Whereby whole cities have **escap'd** the plague,
And thousand desperate maladies been **cur'd**?

The god thou **serv'st** is thine own appetite,
Wherein is **fix'd** the love of Belzebub:
To him I'll build an altar and a church ...

In this passage, it can be seen that the author reflects connotative meanings such as pleasantness, softness, flatness, lightness, comfort, smoothness, fluidity by omitting the unstressed syllables in the words. Elisions with different connotative meanings can also be seen in the following texts:

What dire offence from **am'rous** causes springs,
What mighty contests rise from trivial things,
I sing — This verse to Caryl, Muse! is due:
This, **ev'n** Belinda may vouchsafe to view...
Say what strange motive, Goddess! could compel
A well-bred Lord **t'** assault a gentle Belle?
O say what stranger cause, yet **unexplor'd**,
Could make a gentle Belle reject a Lord ...
Sol **thro'** white curtains shot a **tim'rous** ray,
And **op'd** those eyes that must eclipse the day;
Now lap-dogs give themselves the rousing shake...

In the above excerpt from A.Pope's poem «Rape of Lock» the words *amorous* – *am'rous*, *even* – *ev'n*, *unexplored* – *unexplor'd*, *through* – *thro'*, *opened* – *op'd*, *t' – the*, *timorous* – *tim'rous* are shortened and have forms with elided sounds. In this way, the poet used elision in order to achieve pentameter poetic rhythm, that is, the required number of syllables in the flow of the poem. As a result, the musicality and melodiousness of the poem increased.

Speech with elision is often formed in the process of careless, indifferent, informal, simple, temporary conversation between people. The phenomenon of elision can be used deliberately and knowingly by the writer in the speech of a character in prose, in addition to poetry. From the phonostylistic point of view, it appears that the pronunciation of words with elided sound in phonetic structure has an excess of connotative meanings [10, 95].

As in English, the phenomenon of elision, which occurs as a result of the dropping of sounds or syllables, also occurs in Uzbek speech. Elision is related to the speech situation and brings out various phonopragmatic relations. For example:

Ay, ko'ngilni qitiqlagan erka gul!
Ay, olamni ko'mgan orzu-sirga, gul!
Qayga desang, men ketaman birga, gul.

In the text, the linguo-pragmatic connotative meanings such as sympathy and entertainment appear (in some dialects, it is natural to drop the sound, but from the point of view of literary language, such cases are also of great importance in expressing the author's attitude) with the deliberate dropping of the sound «r» in the word “*qaerga*”.

One of the important manifestations of the use of words related to oral speech and dialectal lexicon in the literary text is their phonetic reduction. Phonetic shortened forms of words are a product of artistic speech, as well as oral speech:

Hurmatga bo'lib sazovor,
Hammaning bo'b qaddi dol,
Hunarni qib namoyish... (B. Boyqobilov. Toj Mahal).

The Forms “*bo'b, qib*” of the adverbs “*bo'lib, qilib*” in the poetic passage firstly introduced the connotative meaning of tone characteristic of oral speech into the poetic text secondly, the poetic form, that is, it served to arrange the musical rhythm in the poetic verse.

Connotative meanings of elision words in these compared languages are similar to each other in terms of diversity and multiplicity. At the same time, their quantity is more in spoken English.

In both languages, due to elision in words, connotative meanings such as brevity of speech, excitement, haste, politeness, ease, passion, difficulty in pronunciation are expressed. In poetry, it serves to adjust the rhyme, rhythm and melody and to further strengthen the musicality.

Conclusion. Thus, the phenomena of apheresis and elision from the phonetic processes (changes) in the compared languages have important semantic-stylistic and functional-stylistic features in both languages. Such words are mainly characteristic of colloquial and artistic speech styles.

In translation studies, especially in literary translation, it is important to deeply understand the connotative meanings of words with phonetic changes and convey them exactly to the reader.

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